

ABSTRACT BOOK

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"DATA-DRIVEN ENVIRONMENTAL DECISION-MAKING"

of exposure to Cu could determine different epigenetic signatures, which would be carried on into nonexposed generations. Accordingly, daphnids with different histories of past exposure to Cu were exposed to toxic levels of the metal for one generation (F0) and then monitored for three subsequent unexposed generations (F1, F2, and F3), with copper-induced DNA methylation changes, their potential transgenerational inheritance, and life-history traits being recorded. Overall, DNA methylation changes targeted important genes for counteracting the effects of metals and oxidative stress, including *dynein light chain*, *ribosomal kinase*, and *nuclear fragile X mental retardation-interacting protein*. Also, contrasting overall and gene-specific methylation responses were observed in organisms differing in their exposure history to Cu, with different transgenerational methylation responses being also identified among the two groups, without apparent life-history costs. Overall, results confirmed the capacity of Cu to promote DNA methylation transgenerational inheritance in a manner related explicitly to the history of exposure, thereby highlighting the potential for the development and incorporation of epigenetic biomarkers in risk assessment frameworks.

1.05.P-Th015 Transgenerational Transcriptional Responses in *Daphnia magna*: The Role of Copper Exposure History
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Chemical exposures can extend their effects beyond “directly” exposed generations and influence the offspring response to future stressors. Thus, the establishment of transgenerational effects is a powerful phenomenon holding beyond exposure periods. Here, we assessed the transgenerational effects after Cu exposure in the invertebrate *D. magna* at the transcriptional level, while also evaluating the influence of acclimation history on such responses. To do so, daphnids with different histories of exposure, i.e., organisms acclimated in a Cu-enriched medium vs. blank ASTM for three generations, were exposed for one generation (F0) to an elevated concentration of the metal, and then the transcriptional response from F0 and F3 (F3 is the first truly unexposed generation) was inspected by real-time PCR employing an array with 41 genes (involved in detoxification and antioxidant response, DNA damage repair, circadian rhythm, and epigenetic regulation). Results showed that daphnids with different histories of exposure to Cu presented distinct transcriptional profiles at F0 and F3, with nonacclimated organisms showing higher modulation on gene expression. Despite the different exposure histories, histone modifier genes were always found to be transcriptionally altered in F0 and F3, suggesting the involvement of histone modifications in the response of *D. magna* to metal exposure. Besides, markedly distinct transgenerational transcriptional responses were found between the two groups of organisms, with nonacclimated daphnids showing a greater number of genes with modulated expression. Overall, results confirmed the influence of exposure history on transcriptional responses, and the ability of metals to determine transgenerational transcriptional responses across non-exposed generations.

1.05.P-Th016 Marine Pollutant Tributyltin Affects DNA Methylation and Fitness of Banded Murex (*Hexaplex trunculus*) Populations

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Banded murex, *Hexaplex trunculus*, is a marine gastropod whose reproductive fitness can be severely affected by very low concentrations of antifouling compound tributyl-tin (TBT). Tributyl-tin has a strong xenoandrogen impact on snails, causing development of imposex (e.g., superimposition of male sexual characteristic in females), thereby affecting the fitness of entire populations. Tributyl-tin is also known as a DNA demethylating agent and an obesogenic factor. The aim of this study was to unravel the interactions between TBT bioaccumulation, phenotypic responses, and epigenetic and genetic endpoints in native populations of murex snail *H. trunculus*. Seven populations inhabiting environments along the pollution gradient were sampled in the coastal eastern Adriatic. Those included sites of intense marine traffic and boat maintenance activity, and sites with low anthropogenic impact. Populations inhabiting intermediately and highly polluted sites exhibited higher TBT burden, higher incidence of imposex, and higher wet mass of snails than populations on low polluted sites. Other morphometric traits and cellular biomarker responses did not show clear differentiation among populations in relation to the marine traffic/pollution intensity. Analysis of methylation sensitive amplification polymorphism (MSAP) revealed environmentally driven population differentiation and higher epigenetic than genetic within-population diversity. Moreover, decrease in genome-wide DNA methylation coincided with the imposex level as well as with the snail mass, suggesting epigenetic background of animal phenotypic response.

1.05.P-Th017 Genotoxicity and Epigenotoxicity of CMIT/MIT on *Daphnia magna*: Trans- and Multigenerational Effects
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CMIT/MIT (the mixture of 5-chloro-2-methyl-4-isothiazolin-3-one and 2-methyl-4-isothiazolin-3-one) is the biocide consistently detected in the aquatic environment due to its broad-spectrum usage in various industrial fields. The ecotoxicological information of CMIT/MIT is very limited to within-generational toxicity evaluation, though multigenerational exposure frequently occurred. Furthermore, despite a possible role of epigenetics on genotoxicity, their relationship is poorly known in the ecotoxicological context. For that reason, we investigated whether parental (PE) and multigenerational exposure (ME) of CMIT/MIT led trans- and/or multigenerational effects by measuring various phenotypic biomarkers over four consecutive generations. Genotoxicity and epigenotoxicity of CMIT/MIT in *Daphnia magna* were also examined using the Comet assay and global DNA methylation. Our results showed the deleterious effects of CMIT/MIT at various endpoints of *Daphnia*, which had experienced the different exposure histories. Parental effects in the PE scenario can be transgenerational or recovered after the termination of exposure.

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The establishment of transgenerational effects following chemical exposure is a powerful phenomenon, capable of modulating ecosystem health beyond exposure periods

More studies are required to clarify the role and connection between different mechanisms (e.g. epigenetic and transcriptional responses) in such processes

METHODS - MULTIGENERATIONAL DESIGN

Acclimation in Cu-enriched medium or blank ASTM

F0 exposure and recovery from F1 to F3 in clean medium

Arrows: flow of neonates from precedent cultures

White boxes: blank ASTM

Blue boxes: EC20 for Cu

Yellow borders: gene expression patterns assessed

(+) past or present culture in Cu-enriched medium

(-) past or present culture in blank ASTM medium

3 replicates per treatment

Total RNA extracted from batches of organisms (10 per condition and replicate)

Complementary DNA (cDNA) synthesized by retro-transcription from RNA

Array targeted 41 genes and 5 endogenous references

RT-PCR employed cDNA as template

Aim

Evaluate the transgenerational transcriptional effects resulting from copper (Cu) exposure, while also assessing the influence of acclimation history on gene expression

Hypotheses

i) Cu can induce transgenerational effects in gene expression patterns

ii) the gene expression responses of naïve and non-naïve daphnids concerning previous acclimation to Cu will differ

iii) the history of exposure interferes with the transgenerational effects in gene expression patterns

A Real Time PCR (RT-PCR) array specifically designed for *D. magna* was carried out targeting detoxification and antioxidant activities, DNA damage repair, circadian clock functioning and epigenetic regulation

✓ Contrasting transcriptional responses observed between non-naïve and naïve organisms at F0 and F3

Table representing significantly increased and decreased expression (green and ↑↑↑ vs. red and ↓↓↓ cells, respectively) of genes in different treatments (Treat.) compared to the references (Ref.)

GENE	Ref.	Control				Cu ^{+/+}		Cu ^{+/-}		Cu ^{-/-}	
		Treat.	Cu ^{+/+}	Cu ^{-/-}	Cu ^{+/-}	Cu ^{-/-}	Cu ^{+/+}	Cu ^{+/-}	Cu ^{-/-}	Cu ^{-/-}	
Clock			↑↑↑		↓↓↓		↓↓↓		↓↓↓		
TIPIN		↓↓↓				↓↓↓		↓↓↓		↑↑↑	
Crypt1			↑↑↑		↓↓↓		↑↑↑		↓↓↓		
PIWI			↑↑↑				↑↑↑		↓↓↓		
Arg1			↑↑↑		↓↓↓		↑↑↑		↓↓↓		
Arg2			↑↑↑		↓↓↓		↑↑↑		↓↓↓		
DICER			↑↑↑		↓↓↓		↑↑↑		↓↓↓		
HDAC1			↑↑↑		↓↓↓		↑↑↑		↓↓↓		
HDAC3			↑↑↑		↓↓↓		↑↑↑		↓↓↓		
HDAC4			↑↑↑		↓↓↓		↑↑↑		↓↓↓		
HDAC6			↑↑↑		↓↓↓		↑↑↑		↓↓↓		
KMT2A			↑↑↑		↓↓↓	↑↑↑	↑↑↑		↓↓↓		
KMT2C		↓↓↓		↓↓↓	↓↓↓						
KMT2E			↑↑↑		↓↓↓		↑↑↑		↓↓↓		
Egless			↑↑↑		↓↓↓		↑↑↑		↓↓↓		
EHMT1			↑↑↑		↓↓↓		↑↑↑		↓↓↓		
DOT1L			↑↑↑		↓↓↓		↑↑↑		↓↓↓		
NSD2			↑↑↑		↓↓↓		↑↑↑		↓↓↓		
SED1			↑↑↑		↓↓↓		↑↑↑		↓↓↓		
SED2			↑↑↑		↓↓↓		↑↑↑		↓↓↓		
SMYD3			↑↑↑		↓↓↓		↑↑↑		↓↓↓		
KMT5B			↑↑↑		↓↓↓		↑↑↑		↓↓↓		
KAT2A			↑↑↑		↓↓↓		↑↑↑		↓↓↓		
KAT5			↑↑↑		↓↓↓		↑↑↑		↓↓↓		
KAT6A			↑↑↑		↓↓↓		↑↑↑		↓↓↓		
KAT7			↑↑↑		↓↓↓		↑↑↑		↓↓↓		
KAT8			↑↑↑		↓↓↓		↑↑↑		↓↓↓		
SAP18			↑↑↑		↓↓↓		↑↑↑		↓↓↓		
DNMT1			↑↑↑		↓↓↓		↑↑↑		↓↓↓		
DNMT3A			↑↑↑		↓↓↓		↑↑↑		↓↓↓		
MT1			↑↑↑		↓↓↓		↑↑↑		↓↓↓		
RAD52			↑↑↑		↓↓↓		↑↑↑		↓↓↓		
RAD51			↑↑↑		↓↓↓		↑↑↑		↓↓↓		
DDB1			↑↑↑		↓↓↓		↑↑↑		↓↓↓		
MRE11			↑↑↑		↓↓↓		↑↑↑		↓↓↓		
XRCC1			↑↑↑		↓↓↓		↑↑↑		↓↓↓		
CAT			↑↑↑		↓↓↓		↑↑↑		↓↓↓		
GST1			↑↑↑		↓↓↓		↑↑↑		↓↓↓		
GST5			↑↑↑		↓↓↓		↑↑↑		↓↓↓		
GST			↑↑↑		↓↓↓		↑↑↑		↓↓↓		

✓ Different gene expression transcriptional responses also observed between both groups

OUTCOME

✓ Regardless of treatments focused, histone modifier genes were always found transcriptionally altered

mRNA levels of histone modifier genes. Asterisks (*), circles (●) and squares (■) denote significant differences

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TAKEAWAY

Results confirmed the influence of exposure history on gene expression and the ability of metals to determine transgenerational transcriptional responses across non-exposed generations